

RESEARCH ARTICLE

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Drawing a blank – design modelling composite timber elements

Tom Svilans^{1*} and Mette Ramsgaard Thomsen¹

Abstract

The shift towards bio-economies of architectural fabrication necessitates particular consideration of how characterizing aspects of bio-materials such as heterogeneity and anisotropy impact the designed performance of architectural elements. These aspects must be integrated into the modelling and representation of architecture and must be instrumentalised for digital design and fabrication processes. The use of timber in construction is challenging due to its complex material behaviours, and therefore robust methods for predicting and modelling these are crucial for exploiting the timber resource more effectively. In light of this, we focus on developing a holistic and integrated digital modelling approach for glue-laminated timber construction elements that connects the digital design model to the specific material resource and incorporates its material complexity into design simulation workflows. We question the role of the lamella in the glulam blank and trace its agency through a series of four disparate projects, from an initially silent and generic constituent of the blank to a key, operative actor in the design of performance-graded timber products through the added specificity of material composition and a liberation of its form. The first project develops a modelling approach that connects material specification and lamella sizing to free-form timber element geometries. It uses principles of industrial glulam production and knowledge of the anisotropic nature of timber to speculate on new forms of glulam blanks that could arise from a deeper engagement with the glue-lamination process. The second project looks further back in the timber value chain at the processing of the specific forest resource into tailored building elements, attaching a material specificity to the lamella. The third project expands the modelling and prototyping of non-standard glulam blanks into considerations of timber waste streams and aesthetics. The final project aims to further speciate the lamella by tailoring its form as well as its material composition to respond to simulated performance demands. Through these projects we outline the development of a novel digital framework that begins as a modelling approach for free-form glulam beams and grows to accommodate the mapping and allocation of specific, heterogeneous input material. As the digital framework matures, increasingly detailed and interlinked digital simulations of mechanical performance are integrated.

Keywords Computational modelling, Timber, Material modelling, Simulation, Finite element analysis, Performance optimisation

1 Introduction

In response to the global climate crisis and efforts to lessen the impact of construction materials on the environment, new material approaches propose a shift to

bio-economies of architectural production and a thorough engagement with naturally growing materials (Ramsgaard Thomsen et al., 2020). These visions necessitate new modes of working with the heterogeneity and innate temporality of biomaterials and their lifecycles. Such modes require a careful consideration of how this heterogeneity and behaviour is modelled, represented, and instrumentalised for digital design and fabrication processes. This shift has helped spur the uptake of timber

*Correspondence:

Tom Svilans
tsvi@kglakademi.dk

¹ Royal Danish Academy, Copenhagen, Denmark

construction in the built environment. As a result, new approaches to using timber in construction have developed hand-in-hand with digital approaches to modelling and simulating its behaviour. The use of timber in construction is challenging due to its complex material behaviours, and therefore robust methods for predicting and modelling these are crucial for exploiting the timber resource more effectively. In light of this, we focus on developing a holistic and integrated digital modelling approach for glue-laminated timber construction elements that connects the model to the specific resource and incorporates its material complexity into design workflows (Fig. 1).

The development of engineered timber products spans over a century, beginning with the invention and proliferation of the first glue-laminated timber (glulam) beams by engineer Otto Hetzer in the beginning of the twentieth century and settling into a wide array of established modern-day products (Müller, 2000). The principle of aggregating smaller timber components into larger construction elements addresses two primary limitations of using sawn timber: a limited scale and a high variance of mechanical properties (Bowyer et al., 2007). Lamination enables surpassing the size limits of individual logs and a mitigation of the effects of highly variable material properties by distributing their variance throughout a laminated element. Over the course of its development, engineered timber has gradually settled into an array of established products of which beam- and column-like glulams, cross-laminated timber (CLT) panels, plywood, and all manner of particle boards are the most proliferated. In the vast majority of cases, these products are procured as unfinished material inputs: beams and columns are further cut and drilled for specific applications while boards are cut with specific profiles and openings. In the production of glulam beams, this takes the form

Fig. 1 A digital framework for connecting a specific timber resource with detailed modelling and simulation infrastructures is developed. Image by Tom Svilans

of standardised lumber glued together into an approximation of the final workpiece, straight laminations for straight elements or bent laminations for curved elements (Stehling et al., 2017).

This intermediate material form – the glulam blank – is prepared from raw material inputs to receive further operations and to be further processed into a final, finished element. It is very often a near-net shape of the final element: larger than the final object and manufactured at a higher tolerance than the precise end-result. The *lamella* – the constituent component of a glulam blank – is the smallest material unit that is aggregated into an element. As such, the size, shape, and orientation of each individual lamella becomes a key driver for how the highly variable properties of timber are expressed in the final architectural element.

By tracing a common thread through a series of disparate projects, we question the role of the lamella in the glulam blank, from an initially silent and generic constituent of the blank. We trace the gradual activation of the lamella as a key, operative actor in the design of performance-graded timber products through the added specificity of material composition and a liberation of its form. Through the projects we outline the development of a novel digital framework that begins as a modelling approach for free-form glulam beams and grows to accommodate the mapping and allocation of specific, heterogeneous input material. As the digital framework matures, increasingly detailed and interlinked digital simulations of mechanical performance are integrated. The result is a digital modelling approach for glue-laminated timber composites that is tightly bound to the specific timber resource and that integrates its material behaviour through simulated performance (Fig. 2).

This line of questioning and work begins with the challenging of the digital value chain in free-form timber design and construction and, as the view over the timber value chain expands, grows, and integrates more steps, develops into a consideration of how the specific timber resource is transferred from its origins in a tree to its final location within an assembled construction element, and how, in parallel, deep material knowledge of the material can drive predictions of its behaviour and performance.

Our work is developed through a series of research projects and full-scale material experiments in different working contexts to query, test and evaluate new workflows that span between design integrated material specification, analysis, and cross-scale fabrication. The work seeks materialisation methods and digital infrastructures to engage with the wood material more intelligently – both in terms of maximising the efficiency of usage of the natural resource as well as leveraging the idiosyncrasies of wood for the benefit of the design. However, the

Fig. 2 A digital mapping of performance demands on a model of a composite timber element. Image by Ee Pin Choo

challenges of this degree of specificity and integration are yet present. Aligning design intent with concrete materialisation tactics requires a straddling of the two domains – an integrated material practice perhaps emblematic of the digital timber craftsmanship at large scales (Scheurer, 2012) or the growth of the designer-maker figure (Sheil, 2005) in contrast to traditional modes of architecture acting at arms-length from both the material resource and its subsequent processing.

The fundamental question is how, given the ability to shape and deploy complex timber composites with methods of digital fabrication, could these blanks be conceptualised, represented, and modelled, in order to explore their potential for new architectural timber typologies.

2 Blanks and timber composites in architecture

Our previous work establishes a “taxonomy of industrial fibre” in engineered timber products, mapping out the established products according to their constituent component size and handling of material directionality (Svilans et al., 2019). This taxonomy is built as a positioning of established products into a field that is meant to be populated with products and prototypes that somehow fall in-between these established key points, pointing at a possible design space for more speculative glue-laminated timber elements.

This design space is developed from observing well-known timber precedents that activate key characteristics of timber such as its elasticity and anisotropy. Free-form glulam projects such as the Omega Swatch building in Biel and Nine Bridges Golf and Country Club in Yeosu-gun demonstrate the formal and geometric possibilities of conventionally layered glulam beams.

More recent projects in the broader timber field demonstrate a more active role of individual lamellae. The Wisdome project in Stockholm involves CNC-machined lamellae that are mechanically laminated on-site in bending, avoiding the need for prefabricating double-curved glulam blanks. These lamellae are cut and drilled with all joints and necessary fixing points as flat pieces, and then assembled into curved beams during construction (Niebler et al., 2023). The effect of the individual

lamella on the overall element form or behaviour is also demonstrated by Wood et al., 2016 through the activation of its hygroscopic behaviour in self-shaping timber composites.

Other projects explore the bespoke aggregation of glued timber components into large-scale structural members. The Hooke Park Library uses a strategic layout of lumber into large timber portal frames that occupy a space somewhere in-between linear glulam beams and cross-laminated panels (Self & Vercruyse, 2017; Vercruyse, 2019). The Tamedia building in Zurich uses a mixture of softwood glulam columns and beams and engineered beech connective components to create an all-timber structure. The strategic use of a tougher wood species in the connections again shows a localised and strategic allocation of wood products and internal articulations of timber types and forms.

What many of these precedents assume is a more-or-less standardized shape of each timber product’s constituent. In the case of glulam and CLT, graded, sawn lumber is assumed to be the default aggregated component. In this configuration, a lamella is always a rectangular extrusion, formed from the linear sawing of logs into boards and planed on all four sides to a particular cross-sectional dimension. While these assumptions and clear categorisations are extremely useful for simplifying the design modelling and representations of complex timber structures (Svilans, 2021), they bely opportunities to use the nature and properties of wood more cleverly towards specific design scenarios.

The development of an integrated material practice in free-form timber seeks to dislodge this assumption and to look for situations in which a non-standard lamella shape would be useful or even better-suited than a conventional one.

3 Computing timber

The computational modelling of timber can be considered a multi-scalar issue since it involves interactions between small-scale material properties, element-scale geometries and material distributions, and architectural-scale structural arrangements and behaviours (Svilans

et al., 2017). As a highly anisotropic material, the consequences of material orientation throughout the body of a timber element are critical to predict and understand to achieve its best mechanical performance. In this work, this multi-scalar approach has necessitated the creation of a framework that can operate across these various scales thereby connecting local material properties with global measures of performance. Particularly in the case of bespoke glulam blanks, being able to model their overall boundary geometry – necessary for architectural information models – as well as individual lamellae and, in turn, their constituent material make-up is critical to understanding how new arrangements of timber lamellae might impact the mechanical performance of these new blanks.

Therefore, the computational framework developed through this work begins with a constrained glulam model that encodes relationships between lamella size and free-form element geometries. It then proceeds to expand this with models of individual lamellae that are distributed across a heterogeneous timber resource, connecting the material composition of individual components with the overall boundary geometry. A coarse finite element model is introduced here to effect a simulation of mechanical performance across the whole element and transferred onto each lamella as a basis for informing an allocation of variable material quality. This is developed further to increase the resolution of the finite element model and incorporate models of knots and fibre orientation in sawn logs. The concluding project in this work demonstrates the exploitation of the entire framework by modelling a small architectural structure, breaking it down into constituent lamellae, allocating each component to a high-resolution material property map of harvested timber logs, and using the results from a finite-element mechanical simulation that incorporates wood fibre orientation models to evaluate the predicted performance of that particular arrangement.

4 Evolving the lamella

The thinking behind this work is developed through several different projects, each with its own context and role. In such a way, the connecting thread throughout these projects is the increasingly detailed consideration of the role of the lamella and the expansion of the digital modelling framework to include more precise and multi-scalar analysis of designed timber elements. It begins with a series of speculative glulam blanks that explore alternative forms of glulam blanks based on basic material and production principles. It continues with a series of experiments that use gathered material data of sawn logs to achieve a material specificity in the finished product, connecting element geometry with high-resolution scan

data. The third project expands the nature of the input material to include waste timber and broadens the criteria for sorting and allocating from being strictly based on mechanical performance. Finally, the fourth project introduces detailed material models for knots and fibre deviation in finite-element simulations as well as highly bespoke lamella geometries. In such a way, methods of modelling and representing custom blanks are sharpened and the progression also reveals a freeing up of the nature of material inputs (sawn logs to arbitrary forms of timber waste material) as well as a freeing up of the geometries of individual lamellae – the constituent components of the blank.

4.1 Speculative blanks

Engineer Otto Hetzer patented a range of the first glulam products and techniques in the early twentieth century. Among them was the now-common *Hetzer method* for glue-laminating timber beams as well as patents that described the use of different cuts and qualities of timber in different areas of a glulam beam to optimize its strength – now commonly known as a *hybrid glulam*. The Hetzer method popularised the most common way of creating glulam beams – the simple stacking and gluing of linear boards into rectangular beams, with the longitudinal material direction following the axis of the beam (Müller, 2000).

Apart from these, Hetzer's work included a series of notable experiments that went beyond this simple technique, driven by the shortage and resultant rising cost of timber in the early 20th century. For instance, patent DRP no. 125895 in 1900 described a technique for profiling the underside of a beam in bending into a curve that roughly mapped onto its mechanical bending diagram and adding a bent lamination along it to take up the tension forces in bending. The patent DRP no. 163144 in 1903 proposed a curved sawing of a timber board and subsequent bent lamination of a lamella sandwiched between the two halves to align the material direction of the bent lamination with the principal stresses of the beam in bending. These were abandoned for being too complex and costly at the time with the available production infrastructure, however returning to these principles in light of the flexibilities and capabilities afforded by digital production tools today provides an interesting new path for expanding the design space of glue-laminated timber products.

Following this path, we prototype a set of speculative glulam blank types that take on this experimental approach (Svilans et al., 2019), each addressing a particular aspect of glulam production and construction: the use of short off-cuts and cross-lamination in the *voxel blank*, the exploration of elements that are between beams and cross-laminated panels in the reinforced *bifurcating*

blank, the integration of crossing connections into the blank itself in the *branching blank*, and so on (Fig. 3). This offers a productive departure from the established types of timber products and suggests more tailored ways of considering the aggregation of glulam elements. This exploration takes place in close collaboration with industrial partners in architectural design as well as large-scale timber fabrication, and specifically looks at how the agency of timber production can find a place in multidisciplinary architectural design contexts (Svilans et al., 2020). The inclusion of fabrication constraints and parameters into architectural design modelling is therefore an initial step in establishing a broader digital modelling framework for non-standard timber composites.

In these non-standard and functionally-graded glulam beams, the role of the lamella becomes more active, guided by the effect of material orientation and difference in mechanical properties along the longitudinal and transverse axes. The shape of the lamella changes, guided by a notion of material orientation and its consequence on the overall performance of the blank. Digitally, the orthotropic model of wood is used to strategize the allocation of wood segments in a glulam blank.

While the lamella is still generally a rectilinearly sawn lumber component, its role in the glulam blank begins

Fig. 3 Speculative glulam blanks challenge the established types of engineered timber products. Photo by Anders Ingvarsten

to become more active and its allocation becomes more attuned to the specific performance requirements of the particular construction element. The digital modelling of such bespoke components must expand to accommodate an internally-changing lamella orientation as well as questions of how to represent varying material orientations and distributions within a complex, compound timber element.

4.2 Forest rawness

The series of RawLam experiments (Rawlam 1,2 and 3, developed from 2018 to 2022) follows the lamella value chain backwards to its origin in the forest. The exploration begins with a probing of new digital methods in sawmilling such as computed tomography (CT) scans of harvested logs and how these could be incorporated into architectural design practices (Svilans et al., 2022; Tamke et al., 2021a, b, c). Collaborations are established with forestry and sawmilling partners, as well as technology companies and research institutes that study the scanning, modelling, and analysis of wood. These experiments begin with considering the implications of having access to a map of the inner volume of logs before any kind of processing occurs and how subsequent processes might be steered by this new knowledge (Fig. 4). The standard decisions and assumptions in industrial sawmilling are challenged: typical approaches of entirely removing the outside surface of the log – manifest as the natural wane on board edges – and sawing only linear pieces. Instead, the entire process chain of transforming a log into a specific architectural element is taken over and interrogated (Fig. 5).

The lamella gains a new specificity and uniqueness, not only because of its placement or orientation in a generalised log model but rather its specific placement within a *particular* sawn log (Fig. 6).

Having access to the high-resolution dataset of the interior landscape of the wood, the material model gains an increased fidelity. Knots become specific entities with specific locations and forms, no longer simplified features that are incorporated in some abstract way in the model. This allows them to be individually treated

Fig. 4 The computed tomography (CT) scan datasets of logs are analysed for key features such as knots and the pith line. Image by Tom Svilans

Fig. 5 Early experiments play with the expression of rawness in glulam elements. Photo by Tom Svilans

– either avoided or precisely placed within the finished element. The exact form and make-up of a sawn lamella is naturally derivable from intersecting the scan data with the chosen board sawing pattern.

The experiments RawLam 1 and 2 prototype this method, experimenting with the allocation of raw wood and wane in bespoke engineered timber components and trialling a digital workflow that allows the simplified glulam model to be augmented with this specific material data. Here, the lamella is still a rectangular prism and is stacked as in the Hetzer method, however its composition becomes entirely tied to the specific forest resource it is cut from. A density map drawn from the CT scan drives the decisions about which part of the log the lamella comes from: denser and notionally “better” material is allocated around joints and parts of the beam elements that work harder such as the outside surfaces of a beam in bending, and less dense and notionally “worse” material – or material that is part of a knot – is allocated to where the material does not need to perform as much.

RawLam 3 demonstrates a further development of this method through the construction of a free-standing structure composed out of glulam beams sawn from four CT-scanned spruce logs. The challenge is in modelling all lamellae from every glulam beam and mapping them onto the four log scan datasets in such a way that the allocations correspond to the simulated performance demands of the structure. Therefore, the representation of the glulam blank requires another parallel computational process: the material allocator. This guides and informs the glulam blank model by searching for an appropriate place in the log for each lamella to be sawn from. The definition and identity of each lamella therefore becomes important since each now has a unique position and material origin. Here the lamella transforms from a generic object with some dimensional parameters and orientation to a specific object originating from a specific material resource (Figs. 7 and 8).

Mapping and *allocating* become the key actions in this series of experiments: mapping the material properties and orientations in a sawn log and allocating them to particular areas of a laminated timber beam element.

4.3 Residual wood

A further development is demonstrated through a close collaboration with another set of industry partners around the design and construction of a free-form timber lattice structure for an exhibition: the Marina Spa Prototype. This effort connects with smaller and more local contexts of production and brings the speculative glulam blank approach into an architectural design project outside the remit of the research environment. Here, a small multidisciplinary team of architects, consultants, engineers, and researchers is assembled, providing yet another type of contextualisation for the work done with timber composites, this time centred around

Fig. 6 The RawLam experiments seek to use a wider range of material from the forest resource. High-quality wood is allocated to crucial areas such as around joints (left) where lower-quality wood or wood that is typically rejected is allocated to areas of low performance. Photos by Tom Svilans

Fig. 7 The RawLam 3 demonstrator consolidates the prototypical design-to-fabrication process that is prototyped in RawLam 1 and 2. Photo by CITA

Fig. 9 The Marina Spa Prototype is built out of 114 free-form timber elements made up of small segments of reclaimed wood. Photo by Tom Svilans

the development and delivery of a commissioned project (Fig. 9).

The 114 beam elements are fabricated out of timber flooring off-cuts – small segments of residual wood – through a process of glue-lamination. A method typically used for reconstructing circular or elliptical door and window frames is extended and used to assemble the off-cuts into varied curved beams. The method – developed by Winther A/S – uses a combination of CNC profiling and drilling to cut each individual segment out from off-cuts and fix their relative position with dowels before being glued together into the final blank. During the final machining of the element, the dowels are machined away. This method can be described as a *segmented blank*, built up of staggered layers of small segments, each oriented to follow the curvature of the element as closely as possible. The degree of deviation from the curvature is limited by

the fineness of subdivision of the element into segments. This established method is extended in this collaboration to handle free-form curved elements, and the digital modelling approach from the previous experiments is expanded to accommodate the irregularly-shaped segments instead of only rectilinear boards (Fig. 10).

A key development in this project is that, due to the residual and non-standardized nature of the input material, a process of *sorting* and allocating becomes not only necessary but desirable as a way to control the distribution of undesirable features such as knots as well as to control the overall aesthetic appearance of the assembled blank. The sorting and allocation of material here is targeted towards aesthetic ends rather than questions of mechanical performance. Evenness of texture between adjacent segments as well as the avoidance of large knots is prioritized. As a demonstration of

Fig. 8 A performance-demand mapping of the RawLam 3 demonstrator drives the allocation of wood material across the model. Image by Tom Svilans

Fig. 10 The Winther method allows the assembly of highly-curved elements from short pieces without the need for complex pressing infrastructure. Photo by Morten Winther

upcycling wood waste into a high-quality construction element, it also highlights the added necessity of material sorting and filtering in the fabrication approach.

The second main development is the use of the small and irregular format of the input material. The mapping of lamella geometry is constrained by the sizes of available material off-cuts and is no longer free to be drawn from anywhere in a scanned log. As such, the material allocation step cannot assume a generally similar source material – a log – and must contend with a large amount of variability, a hallmark of using reclaimed wood as a material resource. The challenge here is how to model a segmentation of the overall blank in such a way that the segments will fit into the available range of material sizes. This is overcome by mapping the range of available sizes and tuning the segmentation of the model accordingly, iteratively checking the lamella models against the available material until all pieces can be accommodated.

In terms of the lamella, its shape becomes irregular and specific to the final geometry of the finished element rather than remaining a standardised product of the sawmill. The lamella-as-board rather becomes the lamella-as-object, freed from its standardised sawmilling origins and able to take on a bespoke shape before being assembled into the blank. The lamella is now sized and shaped according to where material allocations in the beam element need to be or, on the other hand, according to the dimensional limitations of the reclaimed input material (Fig. 11).

Fig. 11 Sorting and allocation of material is based on appearance and availability of input material sizes. Photo by Tom Svilans

A practical consequence of this is that the production process expands to involve multiple machining operations around the lamination of the segments, thus giving more opportunity for control of the final output at the cost of more labour.

4.4 Free-form beams to free-form lamellae

The culmination of this path for the lamella happens through a deepening of the digital material simulation framework as well as the total freeing of the lamella's form from the conventional rectilinear board. In the Eco-Metabolistic Architecture project, the lamella is explored as a geometrically-complex object in itself, shaped by forces acting on its parent element and informed by its specific material make-up and joints (Svilans et al., 2023). The free form of the lamella is more complex than the segments of the segmented blank since they now include joints and more detailed articulations of form based on simulated forces on the digital model. The model is therefore generalised to accommodate arbitrary forms of lamellae that are linked to a specific timber resource. While here they are mapped onto sawn logs once again, the definition of the resource is similarly free to be defined otherwise (Fig. 12).

The digital model evolves to incorporate a fully orthotropic material model and the finite element modelling of mechanical behaviours. Log and knot models are derived from the CT scan dataset of the sawn log and used to orient each individual finite element, achieving a much more detailed representation of material properties in the modelled element. Simulated mechanical performance is used as the evaluative mechanism to determine an appropriate allocation of these free-form lamellae within the source log using the finite element method (FEM). This supersedes the previous, simplified notion of material “quality” and instead bases the evaluation of the

Fig. 12 The allocation of elements in a set of sawn logs is connected to detailed mechanical simulation of the structure as a whole. Image by Tom Svilans

allocation result on the mechanical performance of the element as a whole, under specific loading conditions.

The modelling framework matures to encompass not only the geometric definition of timber composites and their internal subdivisions into individual free-form lamellae, but also a precise mapping of material properties throughout their volumes, driven by the acquired CT datasets, and an application-specific evaluation of their performance, through mechanical simulation. Since the form and make-up of each lamella is decoupled from the initial constrained glulam blank model, the model handles conventional glulam compositions and entirely bespoke arrangements equally well.

The model thus operates on several levels: the initial overall definition of the glulam element, the subdivision of this element into lamellae or oriented components, the definition of a log model that is derived from CT scanning, the fibre orientation model that describes how material orientation changes around knots and throughout the log, and the orthotropic material model that informs the mechanical simulation of the element's behaviour (Figs. 13 and 14).

The application of this model is demonstrated through the design and fabrication of a small frame structure, composed of bespoke glulam beams that are composed of free-form lamellae, informed by a simulated stress

distribution across each beam. The material orientation is varied in zones of the beam to better align the longitudinal material direction with the principal stress directions, a process which roughly defines the segmentation of each beam into constituent lamellae. The lamellae are then allocated to two scanned logs, from which their actual material orientation and properties are extracted, informing the setup of a mechanical simulation model. Varying the location of the lamellae in the logs therefore leads to different resultant expressions of strain values, indicating the effect of knots and specific material orientations within the log on the stiffness of the lamellae and beams under these particular loading conditions. In this way, the material allocation homes in on a solution that minimizes overall deflection of elements through iterative simulation steps.

The blank becomes a functionalised mechanical model that embeds both the particularities of the material resource as well as its performative expression, at once a representation as well as a tool (Fig. 15).

5 Conclusion

This work generalizes the approach to considering gluelaminated timber blanks from a modelling and materialising perspective: the lamella can be rectangular, or its form can also be arbitrarily defined; its material

Fig. 13 Individual lamellae geometries are placed within the log model, harvesting the specific material orientations and properties from the specific scanned log resource (top). A fibre direction model for knots is implemented (middle) which allows the integration of material orientation changes around knot regions in the mechanical simulation model of each individual element (bottom). Image by Tom Svilans

Fig. 14 The knot fibre orientation model describes local discontinuities in fibre orientation around knot cones. Image by Tom Svilans

composition can be uniform and simple, or it can be highly variegated and heterogeneous and driven by datasets that describe specific resources. In other words, by exploring the extremities of material property mapping on timber components and digital design modelling and mechanical simulation of these compound objects, a

generalized modelling and design approach for glue-laminated timber assemblies becomes tenable.

Assumptions remain – glue-line interfaces are not yet properly characterised or implemented nor are hygroscopic effects on form and mechanical performance – however, in terms of connecting the specific

Fig. 15 Mechanical simulation of the assembly shows the effect of specific variations in material properties, particularly around knots. Image by Tom Svilans

timber resource to the simulation of its material behaviour within arbitrarily arranged glue-laminated assemblies, the approach shows much promise for the exploration of the design space offered by the taxonomy of industrial wood fibre. Future efforts may target integrations of more detailed material behaviours through specific case studies to address these shortcomings.

The value of developing a comprehensive model for laminated timber elements lies in the more intelligent exploitation of the timber resource – not only virgin wood from the forest but capitalising on a variety of material waste streams from timber production as well as demolition or disassembly – and the exploration of a wide design space of speculative timber products. Although leveraging the affordances of timber towards a design intent is not novel by any means, a digital framework for connecting the specific input resource with more and more tailored design intentions and predicting their in-use performance is crucial for working at larger scales and in more diverse production environments.

The specificity present throughout this approach – of resource, of material arrangement, of mapping – remains a challenge, both in terms of the logistical effort required to track and maintain precise links between process steps and models as well as in the difficulty in adapting the non-generic to new and diverse conditions. The benefits of generic, interchangeable elements, graded within wide margins, must be weighed against the challenges raised by tailored and hyper-graded elements presented in this work.

This thread of investigation strives to give agency and attention to an oft-overlooked actor in engineered timber construction: the actual constituent component that is aggregated into a performative building element. By instrumentalising the lamella as a key factor in affecting

how a structural timber element – much less an entire timber structure or building – may perform, another perspective on composing architecture becomes available, one that is based on a thorough awareness and exploitation of the material resources involved. In this way, drawing a blank is not only a matter of representing a geometrically varied assembly of material components with some mapping of properties, but rather a linking of design intent to real, sited materials, their histories, and the behavioural manifestations of their complex biogenic makeup.

The shift towards a bioeconomy of construction necessitates a deep engagement with the complexities of biomaterials, their heterogeneous compositions, and behaviours. Bi-directional interactions between the biogenic resource and the construction element need to be drawn out and activated. Such a transition necessitates a rethinking of established modes of designing and representing architecture, towards architectural models that acknowledge and embrace the conditions and contexts of the natural resources they employ, and – ultimately – towards a much more considered, efficient, and sensitive approach to their exploitation.

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Authors' contributions

The manuscript was written with the contribution of both authors. All authors have approved the final version of the manuscript. Svilans, T.: project conceptualizations, methodology, design concept, computational modelling framework development, supervision, writing – original draft, reviewing, and editing; Ramsgaard Thomsen, M.: project conceptualizations, methodology,

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Availability of data and materials

Data sets generated during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Declarations

Competing interests

The author, Mette Ramsgaard Thomsen, is a member of the academic committee for Architectural Intelligence. However, she was not involved in the journal's review or any decision-making related to this submission. The authors have no other competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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